

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED BY
Christos Mousas,
Purdue University, United StatesREVIEWED BY
Filip Škola,
CYENS Centre of Excellence, Cyprus
Eason Chen,
Carnegie Mellon University, United States*CORRESPONDENCE
Frank Steinicke,
✉ frank.steinicke@uni-hamburg.de†These authors contributed equally to
the workRECEIVED 23 January 2026
REVISED 06 March 2026
ACCEPTED 13 March 2026
PUBLISHED 20 April 2026

CITATION

Li K, Mostajeran F, Rings S, Hertel J,
Schmidt S, Arz M and Steinicke F (2026)
Anthropomorphic AI: a toolkit for
authoring and interacting with intelligent
virtual agents for extended reality.
Front. Virtual Real. 7:1794720.
doi: 10.3389/frvir.2026.1794720

COPYRIGHT

© 2026 Li, Mostajeran, Rings, Hertel,
Schmidt, Arz and Steinicke. This is an
open-access article distributed under the
terms of the [Creative Commons
Attribution License \(CC BY\)](#). The use,
distribution or reproduction in other
forums is permitted, provided the original
author(s) and the copyright owner(s) are
credited and that the original publication
in this journal is cited, in accordance with
accepted academic practice. No use,
distribution or reproduction is permitted
which does not comply with these terms.

Anthropomorphic AI: a toolkit for authoring and interacting with intelligent virtual agents for extended reality

Ke Li^{1†}, Fariba Mostajeran^{1†}, Sebastian Rings^{1†}, Julia Hertel^{1†},
Susanne Schmidt², Michael Arz¹ and Frank Steinicke^{1*}¹Human-Computer Interaction, University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany, ²HIT Lab NZ, University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand

Intelligent Virtual Agents (IVAs), which embody an artificial intelligence (AI) in a humanoid representation, have enormous potential for immersive extended reality (XR) environments to enable natural and engaging human-AI interactions. With recent advances in large language models (LLMs) in simulating human-like text responses, interest in anthropomorphic embodied IVAs has grown across extended reality (XR) research and application domains. However, toolkits for authoring and interacting with IVAs in research remain sparse. Therefore, we present *Anthropomorphic AI*, a flexible and scalable open-source research toolkit for authoring and interacting with embodied IVAs with rich multimodal capabilities, including speech, gaze, gestures, facial expressions, and vision. Our system enables developers to create various embodied anthropomorphic IVAs by customizing foundation models, speech-to-text (STT) and text-to-speech (TTS) methods, and adapting the system prompt to guide interaction. We also integrate various features such as proximity detection, trajectory-based action recognition, and vision-based multimodal prompting for supporting natural human-IVA interaction in immersive XR. We evaluate the toolkit through four use case demonstrations, a pilot developer evaluation, and an pilot end-user evaluation in immersive VR, showing its capability in generating anthropomorphic IVAs for immersive XR applications.

KEYWORDS

extended reality, human computer interaction, intelligent virtual agent, interactive systems and toolkits, virtual reality

1 Introduction

A common underlying principle in the development of many human-computer interaction (HCI) techniques is to allow users to interact with computers using natural human-to-human communication rather than forcing them to learn abstract interaction paradigms (Fink, 2012). To this end, embodying artificial intelligence (AI) models or algorithms in humanoid form through anthropomorphic design plays a crucial role in enabling more intuitive and engaging human-AI interactions. For example, when using anthropomorphic design, humans can more effectively communicate with AIs by leveraging natural, already-learned modalities like speech, gesture, and gaze¹ (Kim et al., 2018). At the

¹ Link to supplementary video: <https://youtu.be/bLYXoobcJOY>

same time, anthropomorphic AI-driven systems could more efficiently decode their complex underlying intents through social cues, such as subtle facial expressions, that are easier and more intuitive to understand for humans (Schmidt et al., 2024), thereby reducing the cognitive effort required for interaction and improving system usability (Kim et al., 2018). Particularly for human-AI interactions in extended reality (XR) applications, where users are often co-located with intelligent virtual agents (IVAs) within the same immersive space, a high level of anthropomorphism in these IVAs plays a critical role in simulating controlled social psychology experiments (Peck et al., 2013), education and training (Fink et al., 2024), immersive storytelling and narrative-driven games (Mascarenhas et al., 2018), and psychotherapy (Kruse et al., 2023a).

Recent advancements in large language models (LLMs) and vision language models (VLMs), such as OpenAI's GPT-4o and Google Gemini, equip IVAs with advanced capabilities to simulate natural, human-like text responses via text prompts. Despite their recency, many studies already demonstrate the capability of LLMs to simulate unique personalities through role prompting (Park et al., 2023; Normoyle et al., 2024) and the generation of context-aware facial expressions, gaze behaviors, and body motions through the function calling capability of LLMs/VLMs (Normoyle et al., 2024). Along with the rapid development of cloud-based neural services such as speech-to-text (STT) and text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis, interest in anthropomorphic IVAs has rapidly grown across HCI research and application domains (Lampropoulos, 2025).

Toolkits that allow modularized, streamlined, and accessible authoring and interaction with customized high-quality IVAs for immersive XR applications, where developers can flexibly select and integrate emerging AI technologies, are important for the advancement of IVA research for XR. While technology start-up companies such as *Convai*² start to provide services for authoring anthropomorphic IVAs, these commercial products often lack transparency in data processing and prompting strategies, making it difficult for researchers to evaluate and modify IVAs' behaviors in a controlled manner. Moreover, the closed-source nature of these products restricts further system-level customization, experimentation, and extension, limiting their usage in research settings. On the other hand, emerging open-source authoring toolkits such as *GPTAvatar* (Robinson, 2024) often lack modularity, multimodal interaction support tailored for immersive XR applications, and adaptability to diverse AI models and use case requirements. Furthermore, most of these existing toolkits have not been evaluated scientifically yet; neither from an end-user perspective regarding the quality of the resulting IVAs, nor from the perspective of the developers using these toolkits to design IVAs.

To further support the XR community in this rapidly growing research domain, we present *Anthropomorphic AI*, a flexible and scalable open-source toolkit for authoring embodied IVAs with rich multimodal capabilities. Our system enables developers to create various embodied anthropomorphic IVAs by customizing behavior through expressive facial expressions and body motions, selecting

and combining various STT solutions, foundation models, and TTS methods, and adapting the IVA's role by prompts to guide interaction and behavior. Furthermore, to support natural interaction in immersive XR, we also integrate features such as proximity detection, trajectory-based action recognition, and vision-based multimodal prompting. As shown in Figure 1, we demonstrate the modularity and capability of our toolkit in supporting the streamlined creation of various anthropomorphic IVAs through four innovative use cases: UC1: *Fictional Character*, UC2: *Virtual Twin*, UC3: *IVA Debate*, and UC4: *Multimodal IVA*. UC1 shows the reconstruction of an IVA representing the fictional character Hari Seldon from an existing science fiction book; UC2 showcases the workflow of creating an IVA representation of a real person; UC3 demonstrates the use of our toolkit for creating multi-agent interactions, for example, simulating a virtual debate; and UC4 involves a sample scene of a user interacting with an IVA using all the above-mentioned modalities in immersive VR. Furthermore, we evaluated our toolkit through pilot studies with developers, providing initial insights into potential improvements and future extensions. Finally, at the IEEE International Conference on Virtual Reality (IEEE VR 2025) with over 1,200 attendees, we conducted an end-user evaluation of the IVA authored in UC2 with 34 participants, through which we benchmark the end users' perception of anthropomorphism, animacy, likeability, perceived intelligence, perceived safety, perceived social presence, and the overall ease of use of the application developed using our toolkit.

In summary, the contribution of this work includes:

- A research toolkit for authoring and interacting with anthropomorphic IVAs, optimized for immersive XR³.
- Four innovative use cases demonstrating the modularity and the diverse design space of our toolkit.
- Pilot evaluation with four developers providing insights into potential improvement and extensions of the toolkit¹.
- Pilot evaluation with 34 end-users demonstrating the capability of our toolkit in creating anthropomorphic IVAs for immersive XR applications.
- The derived technical and user experience design insights, along with ethical guidelines of using the IVA toolkit.

2 Related work

This section gives an overview of the literature on multimodal interaction with embodied IVAs and presents existing IVA authoring and interaction toolkits with their capabilities and current limitations.

2.1 Multimodal interaction with embodied IVAs

The anthropomorphic embodiment of IVAs has emerged as a crucial factor for improving the user experience during human-AI

² <https://www.convai.com/>

³ link to repository: <https://git.informatik.uni-hamburg.de/presence/public/iva-sdk-core-public>

interaction (Kim et al., 2018; Casaneuva, 2001; Song et al., 2025). Unlike IVAs that communicate with users via chatbot- or voice-based interfaces, embodied IVAs, which are typically represented as 3D virtual (anthropomorphic) humans within immersive settings, open up rich multimodal communication opportunities via speech, gaze, gestures, facial expressions, and full-body movements (Wang X. et al., 2024). Previous work has shown that embodied IVAs in XR can improve users' sense of co-presence (Guimarães et al., 2020), foster trust (Gao et al., 2025), and increase communication efficiency (Song et al., 2025). It has also been shown that among different levels of anthropomorphism (e.g., from voice-only to full body), a full-body representation of humanoid virtual agents leads to the highest degree of perceived social presence (Kruse et al., 2023b; Mostajeran et al., 2022; Hajahmadi et al., 2025).

With the presence of diverse multimodal communication channels in embodied IVAs, the question arises as to how these can be designed coherently. Early research on IVAs has shown that a mismatch between visual and behavioral realism (e.g., regarding head movements or gaze) reduces the resulting perceived sense of co-presence (Bailenson et al., 2005) and perceived quality of communication (Garau et al., 2003). Since then, many studies have regarded coherent behavior as one of the key elements for the believability of agents (Gomes et al., 2013; Guo, 2023; Bogdanovych et al., 2015). Other elements associated with multimodal behavior were also shown to contribute significantly to the believability of IVAs, including the expression of emotions, awareness of the environment, and reactivity (Bogdanovych et al., 2016). Thus, even if multimodality is not the focus of a research effort, it can be considered a prerequisite for creating believable embodied IVAs.

2.2 Toolkits for authoring IVAs

Despite these prior findings, key challenges remain in designing, implementing, and evaluating natural human-AI

interaction in XR. To support the rapidly expanding research interests in this field, our toolkit provides a modular and extensible framework that allows XR researchers to author and study IVAs, lowering the technical barrier for creating and deploying custom IVAs in immersive settings.

Toolkits used for IVA creation generally fall into at least one of two main categories: (i) toolkits for modeling and customizing the geometry and appearance of virtual humans, such as *Rocketbox* from Microsoft and *Character Creator* from Reallusion⁴; or (ii) toolkits for authoring the behaviors and interactions of IVAs (Thiebaux et al., 2008). Our contribution focuses on the second category by enabling the design and customization of IVA behaviors and interactions leveraging STT, TTS, and LLM/VLM services. By providing an integration for existing 3D virtual human models such as *Rocketbox* (González-Franco et al., 2020) and *Character Creator*, our toolkit, as well as others from the second category, can remain versatile and independent of graphical updates.

Many prior works have considered toolkits for authoring and interacting with generative agents or non-player characters (NPCs). Enabled by rapid developments in the field of deep learning, several recent frameworks have explored generative human-like agent behaviors within game environments leveraging LLMs (Shi et al., 2023; Park et al., 2023). However, many of these previous efforts primarily focus on 2D environments and characters with limited possibilities for natural interaction, making such frameworks less suitable for XR applications. Two notable early contributions were *BEAT* by Cassell et al. (Cassell et al., 2001) and the *Virtual Human Toolkit (VHToolkit)* by Hartholt et al. (Hartholt et al., 2013). *BEAT* does not focus on the interaction between users and an IVA, but rather on the authoring of multimodal agent behavior, including

⁴ <https://www.reallusion.com/character-creator/>

synchronized speech output and nonverbal behavior. In contrast, the VHToolkit was initially designed for creating interactive 3D virtual humans through predefined, rule-based behaviors and was subsequently extended to support various platforms and XR experiences, including augmented and virtual reality (Hartholt et al., 2019). More recently, the VHToolkit was redesigned to incorporate cloud-based LLMs, STT, and TTS models for supporting enhanced human-AI interactions (Hartholt et al., 2022).

In a similar line of work, various emerging toolkits have also begun to streamline IVA authoring with LLM, STT, and TTS integrations, such as *GPTAvatar* (Robinson, 2024) and *Milo* (Shoa and Friedman, 2025). However, both *GPTAvatar*, *Milo*, and the redesigned *VHToolkit* still lack robust support for multimodal interactions, including vision processing and gesture recognition. Moreover, these previous frameworks typically lack modularity, often integrating only one specific STT, TTS, and foundation model. In contrast, our framework is set up to accommodate a wide range of STT, TTS, and foundation models with a scalable system architecture designed to easily support future integration of new cloud services or local models, enabling more sustainable development of a research toolkit.

Furthermore, systems like *GPTAvatar* (Robinson, 2024) and *Milo* (Shoa and Friedman, 2025) lack user-centric evaluations with end-users. This makes it challenging to assess aspects like social presence and the perceived likability of generated IVAs, which are crucial for benchmarking key perceptual factors for human-AI interaction in XR. Our contribution specifically includes an exploratory study with end-users, providing valuable insights into user experiences and serving as a benchmark for future evaluation of embodied, anthropomorphic IVAs.

It is also important to note that the corpus of emerging commercial toolkits, such as *Convai* and *Reallusion AI-Assistant*⁵, provide quick access to a wide range of features via user-friendly interfaces, which can also appeal to laymen, along with flexible game engine integration into Unity or Unreal Engine for supporting 3D and XR development. However, these commercial products and services are typically closed-source, making them difficult to extend, adapt, or scrutinize for research purposes. They are cost-intensive and feature limits for interactions and API calls, which hinder development, exploration, and can strain research project funds. Our open-source implementation complements these efforts by offering a more transparent, extensible, and scalable foundation that enables researchers and developers to prototype, evaluate, and iterate on novel interaction paradigms for anthropomorphic IVAs in immersive environments.

3 System design and implementation

As IVAs hold enormous potential across diverse research and application domains, it is essential for IVA toolkits to enable

developers to flexibly author agents with varying demographics, behaviors, and integrations with cloud-based services. In this section, we present the design of our system architecture and implementation details to demonstrate how our framework supports the creation of customizable, expressive, and deployable IVAs in immersive environments.

3.1 System architecture

3.1.1 IVA component

At the core of the architecture is the *Agent Base Class*, which provides a structured foundation for creating customized IVAs for various XR applications. As shown in Figure 2, our framework supports modular agent design by allowing developers to define behaviors through interchangeable components such as the *Facial Expression Manager*, *Action Manager*, *TTS Service*, *LLM/VLM Service*, and *STT Service*. These modules can be easily extended or replaced to meet specific application needs. Common *agent attributes*, including name, age, occupation, gender, and description, can also be configured directly. We provide a detailed description of the role prompting strategy in the supplementary materials.

3.1.2 Flexible cloud service selection

Our framework integrates diverse AI models and cloud services, giving developers flexibility in selecting speech, vision, and language APIs. It supports both cloud-based LLM/VLMs, such as Google Gemini and OpenAI GPT-4o, and local models like LLaMA and GPT4All. This allows for tailored deployments: local models enhance privacy for sensitive data, while cloud models offer high accuracy and low latency. While some providers offer end-to-end streaming APIs that combine STT, LLM, and TTS, such as OpenAI's streaming API⁶, our toolkit keeps these components modular. This design enables flexible combinations of services and simplifies integration of emerging AI models as the field evolves.

3.1.3 Multimodal integration

Our toolkit enables human-IVA interaction through speech, gaze, gestures, facial expressions, and full-body movements using a combination of continuous low-level control and LLM-powered high-level decision-making. The low-level controller runs in real-time, processing inputs from components such as a gesture recognizer, which detects user-defined gestures, and a proximity detector, which helps the IVA maintain appropriate social distance. As shown in Figure 3, high-level reasoning begins when a user's speech is transcribed into text. This text is combined with a role prompt describing the agent's persona, available actions, facial expressions, and gaze behaviors. An LLM or VLM processes this structured input and produces outputs specifying body actions, gaze

⁵ <https://www.reallusion.com/ai-assistant/>

⁶ <https://platform.openai.com/docs/guides/streaming-responses?api-mode=responses>

direction, facial expressions, and textual replies. These replies are then converted into custom speech using the selected TTS service. The agent’s animator uses separate animation layer masks for the head and body, allowing independent control. Inverse kinematics and lip-sync services further enhance realism by aligning speech with facial expressions and gaze.

3.2 System implementation

3.2.1 Cloud service manager

As shown in Figure 2, each agent has an instance of the cloud service manager, which orchestrates the selection of the

IVA's STT, LLM/VLM, and TTS models. We have currently integrated Google Cloud's STT service for low-latency and high-quality speech processing and the whisper model for local STT processing (Macoron, 2025). We also integrated the APIs of popular cloud-based LLMs/VLMs, such as Gemini and GPT4o, as well as commonly used local models, such as GPT4all and LLaMA (powered by the installation of an Ollama instance (Ollama, 2025)). The IVA can leverage major cloud-based services such as Eleven Labs, Azure, and Google Cloud for TTS and custom speech generation.

3.2.2 Action manager

Each IVA is assigned an *Action Manager* that interfaces with the IVA's animation controller. Actions are defined in a way that each action corresponds to a pre-recorded animation state. Each agent action class includes an instruction prompt specifying a detailed description of the animation and providing a few shot examples on when the actions can be appropriately applied. For example, as listed below, we provide two culturally distinct greeting motions: *GreetWithQuickBow* and *HelloWithRaiseHand*, each suited for different social contexts. When an IVA embodies a person specifically from East Asia, it is more likely to select *GreetWithQuickBow* for greetings based on cultural norms. Additionally, each action can be assigned a list of labels and categories, from which developers could apply category-based filters to construct distinct IVA behaviors. Currently, we have integrated IVA actions sourced from both high-quality motion capture datasets, such as the Character Creator 4 Motion Plus package (Inc., A. S., 2025), and open-source motion datasets, such as Mixamo (Inc., R., 2025) and Rocketbox (González-Franco et al., 2020), all of which are popular animation assets commonly used in anthropomorphic IVA research and development.

```
public class GreetWithQuickBow : AgentAction
{
    public GreetWithQuickBow() : base(
        typeof(GreetWithQuickBow).Name,
        "An _agent_ quickly _bows_ to _a_
        person. _For_ example, _people_ from _East_
        Asian _cultures_ often _bow_ to _greet_
        others, _say_ goodbye, _or_ apologize.",
        new List<string> { "neutral" })
    }
    public class HelloWithRaiseHand : AgentAction
    {
        public HelloWithRaiseHand() : base(
            typeof(HelloWithRaiseHand).Name,
            "An _agent_ greets _others_ by
            raising _and_ waving _their_ right _hand_
            above _their_ head.",
            new List<string> { "neutral" })
        }
    }
```

Listing 1. Agent action example.

3.2.3 Facial expression manager

Similar to IVA actions, each facial expression state includes either a predefined animation or a blendshape preset, along with an instruction prompt with few-shot samples for contextual usage description. We integrate facial expression animations exported from the Digital Soul 100+ library (CC4) into Unity, offering a wide range of complex expressions based on professional mocap data. Although these assets are not open-source, they are popular and widely used among the XR community for research purposes to create custom IVAs (Sonlu et al., 2025). As a fallback to support researchers who do not have access to these motion capture facial expression animation datasets, we implemented blendshape presets of six basic expressions: sadness, happiness, fear, anger, surprise, and disgust, based on the Facial Action Coding System (FACS) (Ekman and Friesen, 1978) with controllable intensity levels. All of the facial expression animations or blendshape presets can be triggered by LLM/VLM structured outputs. For real-time lip sync, we integrate the Oculus OVR Lip Sync API, which enables real-time lip synchronization by mapping spoken audio to 15 predefined viseme blendshapes⁷.

3.2.4 Gaze behavior manager

To animate realistic eye movements, we integrate the Realistic Eye Movements toolkit (Knabe, 2025), which simulates physiologically accurate eye saccades and micro-movements to mimic natural gaze behavior. It includes Inverse Kinematics (IK) for smooth head and eye transitions between points of interest. Predefined gaze behaviors such as *Look at User*, *Look Away Idly*, and *Look at Point of Interest* can be triggered by LLM/VLM. As a fallback to the paid asset for realistic eye movement, we provide a custom component that supports basic head-eye animations, including blinking and gaze (look-at) behaviors through IK pass of the Unity animator.

3.2.5 Gesture recognizer

The current version of the toolkit integrates an open-source Unity trajectory-based gesture recognizer implemented by Krichenbauer (2025). The gesture recognition plugin supports both hand and controller-based gesture recognition, including custom-defined gestures with pre-recorded gesture samples.

3.2.6 Vision

A virtual camera is positioned at the IVA's eye level to capture the XR environment from an egocentric perspective, simulating the agent's vision. As shown in Figure 4, for broader interaction scenarios, such as in mixed or augmented reality, the camera can be replaced with a webcam or other vision input sources, which allows the IVA to also have visual access to the real world.

⁷ <https://developers.meta.com/horizon/documentation/unity/audio-ovrlipsync-unity/>

FIGURE 4

Vision-based multimodal interaction with IVAs. (a) In virtual environments where users are embodied as avatars with face and hand tracking, the IVA perceives their appearance via a virtual camera and provides context-aware feedback, such as an amused expression and personalized dialogue regarding the avatar’s unique features. (b) Similarly, in physical settings, the IVA monitors the user through a webcam to detect real-world attributes, such as a festive hat, and initiates social engagement grounded in the user’s immediate environment.

3.2.7 Software version

Our toolkit primarily targets the Unity Editor version 2022.3.32f1 using universal render pipeline (URP). The toolkit is compatible with characters commonly used in XR research, such as the open-source Rocketbox (González-Franco et al., 2020) characters and characters from the CC4 software exported with a facial blendshape profile using ARKit conventions.

4 Sample applications and Use cases

Use case demos are essential for evaluating a toolkit’s capabilities and applications (Ledo et al., 2018). We present four novel IVA demonstrations that showcase the toolkit’s flexibility, multimodal interaction support, and adaptability across diverse scenarios. A demonstration of different use cases can be found in the supplementary video.

4.1 The reconstruction of Hari Seldon

Creating fictional characters as IVAs is a key use case in games, entertainment, and XR-based NPC development (Park et al., 2023). Here, we demonstrate the creation and interaction with a fictional IVA: Hari Seldon, the protagonist from Isaac Asimov’s *Foundation* series and one of the earliest sci-fi characters depicted as a holoported agent.

We begin by generating a photorealistic headshot of Hari Seldon using OpenAI’s DALL·E 3. Since the output often lacks realistic facial details, we enhance it with InstantID (Wang Q. et al., 2024), which refines identity-preserving features from a single image.

Shadow removal is performed using PhotoAid (PhotoAid, 2025), and the refined image is converted into a 3D head model via the Character Creator 4 Headshot plugin⁸. We further adjust the hairstyle, body shape, and garments to complete the agent, which is then exported and integrated into Unity as described in Section 3.

A custom voice for Seldon is generated using ElevenLabs’ voice studio. The voice design prompt “A voice that is deep, measured, and resonant, carrying the weight of wisdom and foresight . . .” captures the character’s calm authority and academic cadence⁹. This voice can then be directly used in our toolkit’s TTS module.

Once the IVA’s identity attributes (e.g., age, gender, profession) are defined in the system prompt, users can immediately interact with the agent. The IVA exhibits context-aware behaviors and persona-consistent responses. For example, when asked to predict the empire’s future, Seldon first “*thinks seriously*,” shows a “*bewildered*” expression, and then delivers a thoughtful reply.

4.2 Virtual twin

Representing real individuals as IVAs is a key application of XR, with significant potential in domains like healthcare (Kruse et al., 2023a) and education (Fink et al., 2024). In this demo, we showcase an IVA created from a real person. As with fictional characters, the process starts with a 2D headshot, which is converted into a 3D head model using the CC4 Headshot plugin. Voice cloning is achieved through TTS services like ElevenLabs or Azure, using recorded

⁸ <https://www.reallusion.com/character-creator/headshot/download.html>

⁹ Prompt generated using GPT-4o: “What might Hari Seldon sound like?”.

samples to generate a natural, personalized voice. The IVA is configured by prompting the LLM/VLM with key attributes such as name, age, ethnicity, and personality traits, enabling contextually adaptive behavior. For instance, an introverted IVA may perform actions like *Bashful* or *SlightlyShyLowerHead*, while an extroverted one may exhibit a *Confident Smile*.

However, hallucination remains a challenge, as the IVA may occasionally fabricate false information about the represented individual that was not included in the prompt. To mitigate this issue, fine-tuning the model with a larger set of data specific to the individual is necessary to enhance response accuracy. We discuss the ethical implications of these challenges in detail in Section 6.

4.3 IVA debate

We demonstrate the modularity of our framework through a debate simulation between two IVAs with opposing viewpoints. The toolkit enables the creation of dynamic interactions between agents powered by different LLMs, for example, as shown in Figure 1III, Kevin (OpenAI GPT-4) and Camila (Google Gemini) debating the topic: “Who is the best LLM in the world?”

To showcase customizable behaviors, we created IVAs with distinct personalities. Actions and facial expressions were labeled as “positive” (e.g., *Energetic Smile*), “negative” (e.g., *Angry Pointing*, *Yelling Out*), or “neutral” (e.g., *Arm Stretching*). The positive IVA was limited to positive-labeled actions, while the negative IVA used only negative ones. The result is a compelling contrast: the positive agent displays gestures like *fist pump* and *confident smile*, while the negative one uses *annoyed expressions* and *angry pointing*. This simulation illustrates how tailored IVA behaviors created with our toolkit can support training scenarios in conflict resolution, negotiation, and situational awareness.

4.4 Multimodal interactions

In the fourth use case, we highlight our toolkit’s support for rich multimodal interactions. As shown in Figure 1IV, the IVA recognizes user hand gestures, such as waving, as social cues in immersive VR. When the user waves, the IVA waves back and greets them, potentially offering a more natural way to initiate conversations than traditional input methods. The IVA can also approach the user while maintaining appropriate social distance, in line with XR social norms (Llobera et al., 2010).

Another key capability is visual perception. As shown in Figure 4a, when users are embodied as avatars with face and hand tracking from headsets like the Meta Quest Pro, the IVA perceives their appearance via a virtual camera and responds accordingly. For example, upon seeing an avatar with green skin and sunflower-like hair, the IVA reacts with an *amused smile* and says “*You look . . . interesting!*” Similarly, as shown in Figure 4b, when the IVA sees a user through a webcam and detects a red festive hat, it responds with “*I see that you are wearing a festive hat, are you getting into the holiday spirit?*”. This form of image-based interaction enhances expressiveness, empathy, and contextual relevance, and could significantly improve interaction quality.

5 Pilot evaluation

The toolkit targets two groups of users: (i) developers, who will be supported by this toolkit in the creation of IVAs, and (ii) end users, who will interact with the IVAs authored by this toolkit. To assess the perception among both groups, two pilot evaluations were conducted.

At the University of Hamburg, Institute of Informatics, formal ethics committee approval is not required for user studies that pose no identifiable ethical risks. Prior to the study, we completed an internal ethics screening questionnaire evaluating issues such as informed consent, vulnerable populations, deception, psychological or physiological stress, invasive procedures, and the collection of non-anonymizable personal data¹⁰. As none of these criteria applied, consultation with the institutional ethics committee was not required.

5.1 Pilot developer evaluation

In an initial distribution phase, the toolkit was released to developers, particularly computer science students and employees of different XR-related companies, so that they could use it to create IVAs inside their use case scenarios and provide feedback. After using the toolkit unsupervised for several weeks, we distributed an online questionnaire to them to assess usability, technology acceptance, user experience, and overall opinion. Feedback was collected from 4 developers.

5.1.1 Questionnaires

The questionnaire included standardized questionnaires, as well as open-ended questions. The system’s usability was measured by using the System Usability Scale (SUS) (Brooke, 1996). It consists of ten statements, which participants rate on 5-point Likert scales (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). We also used three subscales of the Extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM2) (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000): intention to use, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use. Each subscale consists of multiple 7-point Likert scales (1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree). In addition, we used the AttrakDiff questionnaire (Hassenzahl et al., 2003) to assess the user experience, which consists of 28 7-point semantic differential scales, the results of which can be aggregated into four dimensions (pragmatic quality, hedonic quality concerning identity, hedonic quality concerning stimulation, and attractiveness). The open-ended questions asked about the developers’ experience using the toolkit, positive aspects, difficulties, and feature wishes.

5.1.2 Participants

Four developers completed the questionnaire, three men and one woman (aged from 27 to 31 years, $M = 29.5$). They stated to have $M = 7.5$ ($SD = 4.51$) years of coding experience and rated their experience with Unity and XR development on 11-point Likert

¹⁰ <https://www.inf.uni-hamburg.de/en/home/ethics.html>

scales (1 = never used before to 11 = expert) as $M = 7.75$ ($SD = 4.57$), and $M = 8.25$ ($SD = 4.86$), respectively. At the time of completing the questionnaire, they had been using the toolkit for $M = 27.5$ ($SD = 12.58$) hours. They had received different types of tutorials provided by the toolkit developers, such as an online seminar ($N = 3$), an in-person tutorial ($N = 3$), a video tutorial ($N = 1$), and a written tutorial ($N = 1$). Developers used our toolkit to build IVAs for various application domains, each focusing on one or more domains, including healthcare ($N = 1$), manufacturing training ($N = 1$), professional collaboration ($N = 2$), and human-robot interaction ($N = 1$).

5.1.3 Quantitative results

The following presents the descriptive statistics of the measured usability, technology acceptance, and user experience. The results can also be seen in Figure 5.

Usability. The toolkit yielded a SUS score of $M = 58.75$ ($SD = 14.93$) on a scale from 0 to 100, indicating an "ok" usability (Bangor et al., 2008), suggesting areas for improvement.

Technology Acceptance. For all measured subscales, the mean TAM2 rating was positive, with an *Intention to Use* of $M = 5.00$ ($SD = 0.76$), a *Perceived Usefulness* of $M = 5.00$ ($SD = 0.89$), and a *Perceived Ease of Use* of $M = 4.44$ ($SD = 1.09$) on a scale from 1 to 7.

User Experience. The AttrakDiff scores were adjusted by subtracting 4 to reach a range from -3 to $+3$. The results yielded a *Pragmatic Quality* of $M = 0.25$ ($SD = 0.97$), a *Hedonic Quality (Identity)* of $M = 0.86$ ($SD = 0.76$), a *Hedonic Quality (Stimulation)* of $M = 1.25$ ($SD = 0.29$), and an *Attractiveness* of $M = 0.75$ ($SD = 0.56$). These scores indicate overall neutral to positive evaluations, with higher hedonic than pragmatic qualities.

5.1.4 Qualitative results

The answers given to the open questions were analyzed following a thematic analysis approach (Clarke and Braun, 2014), which was initially carried out by one author. The results were then discussed and refined with another author. The following gives a summary of the retrieved insights.

5.1.4.1 Toolkit usage

Overall, the developers appreciated the open-source approach and the fact that developers are encouraged to contribute to the toolkit. The easy integration of the toolkit in Unity was also positively mentioned. Developers appreciated the compatibility with various services and APIs, as well as the possibility to integrate local models. The multimodality, in particular the agent's vision, was praised. In comparison to other toolkits the developers had used before, our toolkit was perceived as more convenient to use as it is non-commercial and does not rely on external servers. Its large scope of out-of-the-box features was appreciated, but also described as probably too complex for narrow and specific use cases. When asked explicitly, all developers affirmed that they would use the toolkit again and would recommend it to others.

5.1.4.2 Toolkit challenges and wishes

In terms of challenges, the server integration and multiplayer support were described as difficult, but were eventually successfully implemented. Various wishes for additional features were collected, e.g., interactions with the virtual environment, such as picking up objects, and a memory for each agent that is stored across sessions to allow evolving characters.

5.1.4.3 Service challenges

In addition to the feedback on the toolkit itself, some developers also provided feedback that depends on the services they have been using through the toolkit. For instance, they noticed a latency in verbal communication with the agent, wished for additional and more natural animations, described the agent's voices as realistic, and had mixed opinions regarding the versatility of style choices, which was both highly appreciated and criticized as too limited.

5.2 Pilot end user evaluation

To assess how real users experience and engage with the IVAs, we performed a pilot evaluation at the IEEE VR 2025 conference, where we demonstrated the toolkit, let attendees interact with an IVA in VR and afterward assessed the quality of interaction, perceived social presence, and overall usability of the IVAs.

5.2.1 Technical setup

We conducted the evaluation using a Meta Quest Pro HMD connected to a Windows PC with an RTX 3080 GPU. The IVA leveraged Google Gemini as the VLM, Google Cloud for STT, and ElevenLabs for TTS with a cloned voice of the represented individual. As shown in Figure 4a, users were embodied in avatars supporting face, eye, and hand tracking. When vision-related keywords (e.g., “see”, “look”) were detected, the system captured a snapshot from the IVA’s perspective and sent it to the VLM to enhance contextual understanding. The demo supported English STT. The application was created using a template sample scene which is released alongside our toolkit.

5.2.2 Questionnaires

Participants were asked to fill out a survey to assess their perception of the IVA. The Godspeed questionnaire (Bartneck et al., 2009) was used to measure the perception across five sub-scales (anthropomorphism, animacy, likeability, perceived intelligence, and perceived safety). It includes 24 items, 3 to 6 per sub-scale, each rated on a 5-point semantic differential scale. To assess the social presence, two items from the Social Presence questionnaire (Bailenson et al., 2003) were used, which focus on aspects not covered by Godspeed. Participants rated: i) “I perceive that I am/was in the presence of another person in the room with me,” and ii) “I feel that the person is/was watching me and is/was aware of my presence,” on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = fully disagree to 7 = fully agree). We also administered the Perceived Ease of Use subscale of the Extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM2) (see Section 5.1.1)

5.2.3 Procedure

Conference attendees interacted with an IVA representing one of the presenters, featuring her cloned voice and appearance. Before the demo, participants were informed that system usage data would be collected during their interaction and that, with consent, we would gather optional subjective feedback afterward. We emphasized that all data would remain anonymous and would be used solely for research purposes. We also informed the participants that we integrated AI-based services into the application, and we could not fully control the output given by the LLM. Furthermore, we informed participants that although there are policies in place that filter out certain content, such as hate speech, violence, harassment, illegal activities, self-harm, harm to others, or misinformation, there are ways to bypass this filtering, and the LLMs are not customized to individual tolerances and preferences. As a result, we asked the participants not to share any personal or sensitive data with the IVA and that they could withdraw their participation at any time. Consent was obtained verbally and via a digital form.

5.2.4 Participants

In total, we collected survey responses from 34 participants. While we did not collect any personal information, we observed

that participants were primarily academics and XR experts familiar with virtual agents and AI, representing a diverse range of ages, genders, and ethnic backgrounds. Notably, one participant disclosed after the session that he had been diagnosed with Asperger’s syndrome. His data was retained in our analysis to ensure we derive diverse insights from participants’ feedback.

5.2.5 Results

A total of 43 participants interacted with the system (34 completed the survey), generating about 120.5 min of dialogue over 429 interaction rounds. The end-to-end STT latency could not be measured due to real-time audio streaming and incremental transcription. However, the average STT interaction and processing time was 5.579 s, indicating users generally give shorter inputs to IVAs. The Gemini model responded in 1.06 s on average, while TTS response times varied depending on the length of the text input, with the TTS response time alone averaging 2.3 s or approximately 0.085 s per token. The following presents the descriptive statistics of the measured perception, technology acceptance, and social presence. Plots of different metrics can also be seen in Figure 6.

5.2.5.1 Perception

Average scores of the Godspeed questionnaire ranged from neutral to positive. On a scale from 1 to 5, *Anthropomorphism* received a neutral rating of $M = 3.02$ ($SD = 0.7$), while *Animacy* was slightly higher with $M = 3.5$ ($SD = 0.7$), indicating the agent was perceived as somewhat lifelike. *Likeability* scored very positively with $M = 4.15$ ($SD = 0.68$), showing a strong favorable impression. *Perceived Intelligence* was also positive with $M = 3.79$ ($SD = 0.62$), and *Perceived Safety* ranged from neutral to positive with $M = 3.48$ ($SD = 0.63$).

5.2.5.2 Technology acceptance

Averaged over all participants, the *Ease of Use* scale of the TAM2 questionnaire was rated as very positive with a score of $M = 5.61$ ($SD = 1.03$), on a scale from 1 to 7.

5.2.5.3 Social presence

For both scales of the Social Presence questionnaire, the scores were adjusted by subtracting 4 to reach a range from -3 to $+3$, then averaged per participant and across all participants (Mostajeran et al., 2020). A positive mean score of $M = 1.19$ ($SD = 0.95$) indicates that participants felt the IVA was socially present in the virtual environment.

6 Discussion

The use case demonstrations, developer evaluation, and end-user evaluation provide valuable insights both into the advantages and limitations of the technical implementation of the toolkit and into end-user experiences of an application developed with our toolkit, which we discuss in detail in this section.

6.1 Technical design insights

6.1.1 Token consumption

To generate believable IVA behaviors, our framework relies on short text descriptions (1–2 sentences) of possible actions and facial expressions, as detailed in Section 3. In our demo, the IVA could perform 36 facial expressions and 48 body movements, resulting in roughly 2,800 tokens in system prompts. While many LLM/VLM services offer caching to reduce token usage, handling this volume can become costly over time. To address this, we implemented that developers can choose between two description modes in our toolkit: a “simple” mode that transmits only the names of actions and expressions (around 549 tokens), and a “detailed” mode that includes full descriptions. Moreover, our system has primarily been tested with short to medium-length conversations. We expect that longer interactions increase token usage, as the full chat history is sent with each query. This can lead to high costs when using cloud-based services. In future work, we plan on implementing a memory and reflection mechanisms (Park et al., 2023) to optimize token efficiency during extended interactions.

6.1.2 Service selections and latency

When using local models, there is often a trade-off between model size and inference latency: larger models with more parameters generally produce more accurate and reliable results, but at the cost of longer response times. To balance performance and efficiency, most of our demonstrations rely on cloud-based services, where latency reduction techniques are already optimized by the service providers. To further minimize perceived latency, we initiate the IVA’s animations immediately after receiving responses from the LLM/VLM, while the TTS cloud service concurrently synthesizes audio. In our tests, Google Gemini exhibited lower latency than OpenAI’s GPT-4o when handling multimodal prompts involving images. For TTS, Microsoft Azure provided the lowest latency among popular cloud-based services, due to its asynchronous audio streaming capabilities. We also observed during end-user

tests that the current STT models have difficulties in understanding users with strong accents, occasionally resulting in frustration and reduced usability, further leading to false content generation. To address this, we have already integrated multi-lingual capabilities of STT and TTS services into our framework. To further improve accessibility, future developments of our toolkit will consider integrating STT models that are more robust to diverse accents, enabling a more inclusive user experience. Recently, we integrated the Gemini streaming API, which significantly reduces processing latency and enables near real-time IVA interaction (Google DeepMind, 2025). Recent benchmarks for the Gemini 2.5 Flash Live API demonstrate a significant reduction in the traditional pipeline delay, reaching a median Time to First Token (TTFT) of 340 ms–420 ms (Artificial Analysis, 2026). Beside low-latency, this integration offers several advantages: simple setup using a single Google Cloud API key, rapid prototyping for new developers, built-in short-term memory without external handling of conversation history, and support continuous video streaming with concurrent task execution such as action recognition. However, this solution does not support modular customization, for example, integrating third-party voice services like ElevenLabs while using alternative LLM/VLM models from other cloud services, and it reduces system transparency since all processing is encapsulated within a single model.

6.1.3 Developer insights

The evaluation of the toolkit from a developer’s perspective indicates that developers particularly appreciate the open-source approach and modular integration of local and external services. An acceptable usability was measured and up to now, no integration challenges were reported that could not be solved eventually. Most issues observed by developers, such as latency, depend on the AI models and services used. However, the toolkit’s scalable architecture allows developers to integrate additional cloud services and local models to author agents according to their specific requirements. Besides pragmatic qualities, hedonic qualities were rated positively, indicating a fulfilling experience authoring intelligent virtual agents.

6.2 End-user experiences (UX) design insights

While most participants responded positively to the ease of use of our application, noting that their interaction with it felt clear and understandable and did not demand significant mental effort, for future studies and real-world applications, we recommend developers considering the following UX insights that we have identified:

6.2.1 Maintaining social presence

Our pilot end-user evaluation further validates prior findings that users experience a strong sense of social presence when interacting with anthropomorphic embodied IVAs in immersive XR environments (Kim et al., 2018). For example, we observed one participant repeatedly nodding in approval while the IVA was speaking, despite having been informed that the agent would only record speech when a “listening” indicator appeared above its head. Another participant engaged in an extended conversation with the IVA and continued responding even while removing the headset. They, along with several others, later explained that they felt compelled to remain polite toward the agent, despite feeling fatigued and not initially intending to speak for so long. These behaviors align with the positive evaluations on the social presence metric. However, maintaining a strong sense of presence during extended, in-the-wild human-AI interactions requires more detailed consideration of IVA design. For instance, multiple participants reported difficulties interrupting the IVA during long responses. Others found it challenging to come up with topics to discuss with the IVA. Although we primarily evaluated the application in an immersive VR environment, most participants naturally steered the conversation toward topics related to the conference venue and its surroundings. These observations suggest that there are various design aspects to be further investigated to create IVAs that can maintain strong social presence over longer interaction periods. We suggest future work to further investigate how IVAs can better support natural turn-taking, better encourage topic suggestions when the user is unsure what to say, and adapt to the situational context across the reality-virtuality spectrum via the multimodal interaction capabilities enabled by our toolkit.

6.2.2 Diversity of users and IVAs

We observed a wide range of interaction behaviors with the IVAs. In particular, the qualitative feedback revealed significant individual differences in how participants perceived the same IVA behaviors. For example, a Japanese participant noted that prolonged eye contact felt impolite in their cultural context, while a visitor from the USA specifically appreciated the IVA’s frequent eye contact during conversation. This highlights the need for IVA designs to accommodate diverse cultural backgrounds. Additionally, developers should consider enhancing the accessibility of IVA interactions. One participant with Asperger’s syndrome, for instance, reported difficulty interpreting the IVA’s facial expressions. In such cases,

the IVA should be able to adjust its emotional expressiveness accordingly, for example, by presenting clearer, more exaggerated facial emotions aligned with voice cues, while also maintaining gentler and customizable eye contact behaviors (Damm et al., 2013). Developers could further support inclusivity by offering user-adjustable options for gaze behavior and agent proximity, tailored to individual preferences and needs.

6.2.3 Evaluation limitations

To evaluate the perception and value of the toolkit, we conducted pilot evaluations with two target user groups: developers and end-users. In particular, the pilot developer evaluation includes only a small number of participants, due to the early stage of deployment and therefore limited developer community. In both pilot evaluations, only descriptive exploratory findings were gathered. In the future, we will evaluate both the toolkit itself and the IVAs generated with the toolkit in a controlled environment, employing hypothesis-based evaluations. Further, our evaluation is limited in terms of the diversity of the IVA and also the users. As mentioned, the users were mostly experts in this field and their evaluation might lack generalizability to other target groups. Future studies should include a more diverse group of users with different backgrounds and levels of expertise with the technologies that are used in this toolkit.

7 Ethical considerations

Using our toolkit involves several ethical considerations. In our studies, we addressed key ethical concerns in the consent form and briefly explained them to each participant and developer. However, additional ethical aspects need to be taken into account when deploying the full toolkit more broadly.

In the first place, when creating a digital twin of a living or dead person, one should take into account the rights of accessing and using their personal information, including their biometric data. One way to tackle this issue is through informed consent, where the user grants clear consent for processing their personal information for this specific purpose. Informed consent requires that individuals are aged 16 or older and are of sound mind, fully understand and voluntarily agree to the terms and implications of a decision before proceeding. Proxy consent needs to be received for other groups of individuals, including minors, incapacitated, or deceased individuals.

An important ethical and technical concern when using our toolkit is the limited control over the output generated by integrated services such as LLMs, VLMs, and STT models. While LLMs typically implement content moderation policies to filter out harmful content, users may still find ways to bypass restrictions, and the models themselves are not personalized to align with individual users’ sensitivities or preferences. For instance, if the STT component inaccurately transcribes spoken language or if the VLM misinterprets the content of an image presented by the user, the IVA may generate a response that is contextually inappropriate. In a worst-case scenario, a user might raise a serious or emotionally sensitive topic, such as speaking about a tragic personal experience or showing an image of a traumatic historical event, only to receive

an incongruent or even cheerful response from the IVA. Such mismatches may lead to emotional harm or discomfort for users. To mitigate these risks, users must be informed in advance about the possibility of inappropriate or mismatched responses. Developers must also consider these risks from a system design and trustworthiness standpoint, particularly when building IVAs for sensitive domains such as healthcare. One potential mitigation strategy is to make the AI nature of the system more transparent, for example, requiring users to use a wake-up phrase such as “Hello AI” to initiate interactions and to reinforce user awareness that they are engaging with an automated AI system with uncertain outputs and responses.

Finally, while IVAs offer numerous advantages for enhancing user interaction, they also introduce significant risks related to identity theft, misconduct, deception, and impersonation. As these agents become more sophisticated, malicious actors may exploit their capabilities to generate convincing fake identities or simulate human-like interactions, potentially gaining unauthorized access to personal information or financial resources. The threat of misuse is particularly acute in the context of social engineering attacks, where users could be manipulated into disclosing sensitive data under the false impression that they are communicating with a trusted party. Moreover, the ability of IVAs to convincingly impersonate real individuals poses a serious challenge to maintaining trust in digital communication, making it increasingly difficult to verify authenticity in online interactions and transactions. To address these concerns, developers using such toolkits must implement robust security protocols, transparency mechanisms, and ethical guidelines that can help detect, deter, and mitigate such risks.

8 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a modular and scalable toolkit for authoring and interacting with anthropomorphic IVAs in XR. The created IVAs have rich multimodal capabilities, including speech, vision, gaze, gestures, facial expressions, and full-body movements. Within four sample use cases, we demonstrated the usage of our toolkit for authoring and interacting with diverse IVAs, such as representing an existing fictional character, creating a virtual twin of a real person, or simulating a virtual debate between multiple agents. A pilot developer evaluation reveals acceptable usability, with all developers able to use the toolkit to create customized IVAs with multimodal interaction for various applications. All developers reported that they would recommend the toolkit to others and highlighted its advantage in offering a more transparent authoring process compared to commercial tools like *Convai*. The pilot end-user evaluation also shows high ease of use and likability of the IVAs created using a sample demo scene from our toolkit, with users perceiving a positive sense of social presence while interacting with the agents in immersive environments. As the field of IVAs continues to advance, we look forward to seeing how the XR community will adopt and extend our toolkit in their research and contribute to its ongoing open-source development.

Data availability statement

The SDK itself is already publically available (and already linked in footnotes). The raw data of the evaluations will not be made publicly available due to data safety reasons for the participants.

Ethics statement

According to the rules of the ethics commission of the Department of Informatics, University of Hamburg, a basic questionnaire was completed, and based on the results, consultation with the ethics commission for approval was not required. The studies were conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements. The participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

Author contributions

KL: Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. FM: Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft. SR: Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. JH: Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft. SS: Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft. MA: Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. FS: Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing.

Funding

The author(s) declared that financial support was received for this work and/or its publication. The authors received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program for the PRESENCE project (grant agreement No 101135025), and the MSCA Staff Exchanges project PLACES (grant agreement No 101086206), and Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTR) HIVAM project (grant No 16SV8878).

Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that generative AI was used in the creation of this manuscript. Early drafts of this submission were rephrased for clarity and grammatical correctness using OpenAI’s GPT-4o model and Google’s Gemini. However, the original research and analysis were conducted independently by the authors.

Any alternative text (alt text) provided alongside figures in this article has been generated by Frontiers with the support of artificial intelligence and reasonable efforts have been made to ensure accuracy, including review by the authors wherever possible. If you identify any issues, please contact us.

Publisher's note

All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent those of their affiliated

organizations, or those of the publisher, the editors and the reviewers. Any product that may be evaluated in this article, or claim that may be made by its manufacturer, is not guaranteed or endorsed by the publisher.

Supplementary material

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frvir.2026.1794720/full#supplementary-material>

References

- Artificial Analysis (2026). Gemini 2.5 flash: provider performance, latency, and pricing analysis. Available online at: <https://artificialanalysis.ai/models/gemini-2-5-flash/providers> (Accessed January 26, 2026).
- Bailenson, J. N., Blascovich, J., Beall, A. C., and Loomis, J. M. (2003). Interpersonal distance in immersive virtual environments. *Personality Soc. Psychol. Bull.* 29, 819–833. doi:10.1177/0146167203029007002
- Bailenson, J. N., Swinth, K., Hoyt, C., Persky, S., Dimov, A., and Blascovich, J. (2005). The independent and interactive effects of embodied-agent appearance and behavior on self-report, cognitive, and behavioral markers of copresence in immersive virtual environments. *Presence* 14, 379–393. doi:10.1162/105474605774785235
- Bangor, A., Kortum, P. T., and Miller, J. T. (2008). An empirical evaluation of the system usability scale. *Int. J. Human-Computer Interact.* 24, 574–594. doi:10.1080/10447310802205776
- Bartneck, C., Kulić, D., Croft, E., and Zoghbi, S. (2009). Measurement instruments for the anthropomorphism, animacy, likeability, perceived intelligence, and perceived safety of robots. *Int. J. Soc. Robot.* 1, 71–81. doi:10.1007/s12369-008-0001-3
- Bogdanovych, A., Trescak, T., and Simoff, S. (2015). “Formalising believability and building believable virtual agents,” in *Australasian conference on artificial life and computational intelligence* (Springer), 142–156.
- Bogdanovych, A., Trescak, T., and Simoff, S. (2016). What makes virtual agents believable? *Connect. Sci.* 28, 83–108. doi:10.1080/09540091.2015.1130021
- Brooke, J. (1996). Sus-a quick and dirty usability scale. *Usability Evaluation Industry* 189, 4–7.
- Casaneuva, J. S. (2001). Presence and co-presence in collaborative virtual environments.
- Cassell, J., Vilhjálmsdóttir, H. H., and Bickmore, T. (2001). “Beat: the behavior expression animation toolkit,” in *Proceedings of the 28th annual conference on computer graphics and interactive techniques*, 477–486.
- Clarke, V., and Braun, V. (2014). “Thematic analysis,” in *Encyclopedia of critical psychology* (Springer), 1947–1952.
- Damm, O., Malchus, K., Jaecks, P., Krach, S., Paulus, F. M., Naber, M., et al. (2013). “Different gaze behavior in human-robot interaction in asperger’s syndrome: an eye-tracking study,” in *IEEE ro-man*, 368–369.
- Ekman, P., and Friesen, W. V. (1978). Facial action coding system. *Environ. Psychol. and Nonverbal Behav.* doi:10.1037/t27734-000
- Fink, J. (2012). “Anthropomorphism and human likeness in the design of robots and human-robot interaction,” in *International conference on software reuse*.
- Fink, M. C., Robinson, S. A., and Ertl, B. (2024). Ai-based avatars are changing the way we learn and teach: benefits and challenges. *Front. Educ.* 9, 9–2024. doi:10.3389/educ.2024.1416307
- Gao, Y., Dai, Y., Zhang, G., Guo, H., Mostajeran, F., Zheng, B., et al. (2025). Trust in virtual agents: exploring the role of stylization and voice. *IEEE Trans. Vis. Comput. Graph.* 31 (5), 3623–3633. doi:10.1109/TVCG.2025.3549566
- Garau, M., Slater, M., Vinayagamoorthy, V., Brogni, A., Steed, A., and Sasse, M. A. (2003). “The impact of avatar realism and eye gaze control on perceived quality of communication in a shared immersive virtual environment,” in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 529–536. doi:10.1145/642611.642703
- Gomes, P., Paiva, A., Martinho, C., and Jhala, A. (2013). “Metrics for character believability in interactive narrative,” in *International conference on interactive digital storytelling* (Springer), 223–228.
- González-Franco, M., Ofek, E., Pan, Y., Antley, A., Steed, A., Spanlang, B., et al. (2020). The rocketbox library and the utility of freely available rigged avatars. *Front. Virtual Real.* 1. doi:10.3389/frvir.2020.561558
- Google DeepMind (2025). *Multimodal live Api developer guide*. Available online at: <https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs/multimodal-live> (Accessed March 02, 2026).
- Guimarães, M., Prada, R., Santos, P. A., Dias, J., Jhala, A., and Mascarenhas, S. F. (2020). “The impact of virtual reality in the social presence of a virtual agent,” in *Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on intelligent virtual agents*.
- Guo, S. (2023). “Developing a scale for measuring the believability of virtual agents,” in *International conference on artificial reality and teleexistence and eurographics symposium on virtual environments (ICAT-EGVE) (eurographics digital library)*.
- Hajahmadi, S., Cascarano, P., Mostajeran, F., Heuer, K., Lux, A., Mends-Cole, G. O., et al. (2025). “Investigating the impact of voice-only and embodied conversational virtual agents on mixed reality puzzle solving,” in *2025 IEEE conference virtual reality and 3D user interfaces (VR)* (IEEE), 602–612.
- Hartholt, A., Traum, D., Marsella, S., Shapiro, A., Stratou, G., Leuski, A., et al. (2013). “All together now,” in *International conference on intelligent virtual agents*.
- Hartholt, A., Fast, E., Reilly, A., Whitcup, W., Liewer, M., and Mozgai, S. (2019). “Ubiquitous virtual humans: a multi-platform framework for embodied ai agents in xr,” in *2019 IEEE international conference on artificial intelligence and virtual reality (AIVR)*, 308–3084. doi:10.1109/AIVR46125.2019.00072
- Hartholt, A., Fast, E., yong Li, Z., Kim, K., Leeds, A., and Mozgai, S. (2022). “Re-architecting the virtual human toolkit: towards an interoperable platform for embodied conversational agent research and development,” in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM international conference on intelligent virtual agents*.
- Hassenzähl, M., Burmester, M., and Koller, F. (2003). “Attrakdiff: Ein fragebogen zur messung wahrgenommener hedonischer und pragmatischer qualität,” in *Mensch und computer 2003: interaktion in bewegung* (Springer), 187–196.
- Inc., A. S. (2025). *Mixamo: 3D character animation software*.
- Inc., R. (2025). *Character creator 4: 3d character creation software*.
- Kim, K., Boelling, L., Haesler, S., Bailenson, J. N., Bruder, G., and Welch, G. (2018). “Does a digital assistant need a body? The influence of visual embodiment and social behavior on the perception of intelligent virtual agents in ar,” in *2018 IEEE international symposium on mixed and augmented reality (ISMAR)*, 105–114.
- Knabe, T. (2025). *Realistic eye movements*, 12. Available online at: URL: <https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/tools/animation/realistic-eye-movements-29168>.
- Krichenbauer, M. (2025). *Mivry 3d gesture recognition ai*. Available online at: <https://github.com/MARUI-Plugin/MiVRy> (Accessed April 1, 2025).
- Kruse, L., Hertel, J., Mostajeran, F., Schmidt, S., and Steinicke, F. (2023a). “Would you go to a virtual doctor? A systematic literature review on user preferences for embodied virtual agents in healthcare,” in *2023 IEEE international symposium on mixed and augmented reality (ISMAR)*, 672–682.
- Kruse, L., Mostajeran, F., and Steinicke, F. (2023b). “The influence of virtual agent visibility in virtual reality cognitive training,” in *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM symposium on spatial user interaction*, 1–9.
- Lampropoulos, G. (2025). Intelligent virtual reality and augmented reality technologies: an overview. *Future Internet* 17, 58. doi:10.3390/fi17020058
- Ledo, D., Houben, S., Vermeulen, J., Marquardt, N., Oehlberg, L., and Greenberg, S. (2018). “Evaluation strategies for hci toolkit research,” in *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*.
- Llobera, J., Spanlang, B., Ruffini, G., and Slater, M. (2010). Proxemics with multiple dynamic characters in an immersive virtual environment. *ACM Trans. Appl. Percept.* 8 (3), 1–3. doi:10.1145/1857893.1857896
- Macoron (2025). *Whisper.unity*. Available online at: <https://github.com/Macoron/whisper.unity> (Accessed April 1, 2025).
- Mascarenhas, S. F., Guimarães, M., Prada, R., Dias, J., Santos, P. A., Star, K., et al. (2018). “A virtual agent toolkit for serious games developers,” in *2018 IEEE conference on computational intelligence and games (CIG)*, 1–7.

- Mostajeran, F., Steinicke, F., Ariza Nunez, O. J., Gatsios, D., and Fotiadis, D. (2020). "Augmented reality for older adults: exploring acceptability of virtual coaches for home-based balance training in an aging population," in *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, 1–12.
- Mostajeran, F., Burke, N., Ertugrul, N., Hildebrandt, K., Matov, J., Tapie, N., et al. (2022). "Anthropomorphism of virtual agents and human cognitive performance in augmented reality," in *2022 IEEE conference on virtual reality and 3D user interfaces abstracts and workshops (VRW) (IEEE)*, 329–332.
- Normoyle, A., Sedoc, J., and Durupinar, F. (2024). "Using llms to animate interactive story characters with emotions and personality," in *2024 IEEE conference on virtual reality and 3D user interfaces abstracts and workshops (VRW)*, 632–635.
- Ollama (2025). Ollama. Available online at: <https://github.com/ollama/ollama> (Accessed April 1, 2025).
- Park, J. S., O'Brien, J. C., Cai, C. J., Morris, M. R., Liang, P., and Bernstein, M. S. (2023). "Generative agents: interactive simulacra of human behavior," in *Proceedings of the 36th annual ACM symposium on user interface software and technology*.
- Peck, T. C., Seinfeld, S., Aglioti, S. M., and Slater, M. (2013). Putting yourself in the skin of a Black avatar reduces implicit racial bias. *Conscious. Cognition* 22, 779–787. doi:10.1016/j.concog.2013.04.016
- PhotoAid (2025). *Remove shadow from photo - ai shadow remover*.
- Robinson, S. (2024). GPTAvatar: a 3D AI virtual chatbot made in Unity.
- Schmidt, S., Rolf, T., Voigt, H., Offe, M., and Steinicke, F. (2024). "Natural expression of a machine learning model's uncertainty through verbal and non-verbal behavior of intelligent virtual agents," in *ACM symposium on user interface software and technology*.
- Shi, J., Zhao, J., Wang, Y., Wu, X., Li, J., and He, L. (2023). *CGMI: configurable general multi-agent interaction framework*. *ArXiv Abs/2308*. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2308.12503
- Shoa, A., and Friedman, D. (2025). Milo: an llm-based virtual human open-source platform for extended reality. *Front. Virtual Real.* 6, 6–2025. doi:10.3389/frvir.2025.1555173
- Song, T., Pabst, F., Eck, U., and Navab, N. (2025). Enhancing patient acceptance of robotic ultrasound through conversational virtual agent and immersive visualizations. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*. 31 (5), 2901–2911. doi:10.1109/TVCG.2025.3549181
- Sonlu, S., Bendiksen, B., Durupinar, F., and Gudukbay, U. (2025). "Effects of embodiment and personality in llm-based conversational agents," in *2025 IEEE conference virtual reality and 3D user interfaces (VR)*, 718–728.
- Thiebaux, M., Marsella, S., Marshall, A. N., and Kallmann, M. (2008). "SmartBody: behavior realization for embodied conversational agents," in *Proceedings of the International Joint Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems*. 151–158.
- Venkatesh, V., and Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: four longitudinal field studies. *Manag. Science* 46, 186–204. doi:10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926
- Wang, Q., Bai, X., Wang, H., Qin, Z., and Chen, A. (2024a). *Instantid: zero-Shot identity-preserving generation in seconds*. *ArXiv abs/2401.07519*.
- Wang, X., Cao, N., Chen, Q., and Cao, S. (2024b). The interaction design of 3d virtual humans: a survey. *Comput. Sci. Rev.* 53, 100653. doi:10.1016/j.cosrev.2024.100653